

hydrazone, m.p. 157°. **2** (0.2 g) with 2 N H₂SO₄ (1.4 ml) yielded gelatinous D-allose (**4**; 0.12 g), m.p. 128° [α]_D+7° (H₂O); it formed an osazone, m.p. 173°.

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Chemical Examination of *Buddleia neemda*

B. Ham.

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IN connection with our work on plant pigments¹, phytochemical investigation of *Buddleia neemda* B. Ham. (Syn. *B. asiatica* Lour.; loganiaceae)² has been undertaken. *B. neemda* is a very common shrub occurring throughout India and is used as an indigenous drug in the treatment of skin diseases. Literature survey reveals that the flowers of this plant have been investigated earlier³. We now report the results of chemical examination of the aerial parts (stems and leaves) of this plant on which no work has been done so far.

The air dried powdered aerial parts (stems and leaves) of *B. neemda* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene–chloroform (3 : 1) mixture afforded yellow needles, C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (*M*⁺ 314), m.p. 280°, crystallised from benzene. It gave greenish blue colour with ferric chloride and responded magnesium–hydrochloric acid test for flavonoids. It was found to contain two methoxy groups as indicated by Zeisel experiment and exhibits $\lambda_{\max}$ 255, 310 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200 (br, bonded-OH), 1650, 1605 and 1580 cm⁻¹ (chelated α,β -unsaturated C=O). These spectral data in conjunction with the fact that the compound forms a monomethyl ether, C₁₈H₁₆O₆ (*M*⁺ 328), m.p. 160° on treatment with diazomethane, and a dimethyl ether, C₂₀H₁₈O₆ (*M*⁺ 342), m.p. 188° on reaction with dimethyl sulphate reveals that the compound is a dihydroxydimethoxyflavone. Finally, the flavone was characterised as 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone from the comparison of physical properties of this compound and its mono- and dimethyl derivatives respectively with those of the aglycone of 3',4'-dimethylfluteolin-7-O- β -D-glucopyranuronide⁴, 7,3',4'-trimethylfluteolin⁵ and 5,7,3',4'-

tetramethylfluteolin⁶. Incidentally, it appears to be the first report of isolation of this flavone from natural source.

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Chemical Constituents of *Nephrolepis tuberosa*

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IN the course of our investigation on different Indian ferns having insecticidal and biological activity, we undertook the systematic chemical investigation of a hitherto uninvestigated plant, *Nephrolepis tuberosa* (Fam.: *Pteridophytes*), popularly known as *Pani Amla*, which grows abundantly in the Eastern Himalayan region.

The light petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the powdered stem and leaves of *N. tuberosa* upon chromatography over silica gel afforded β -sitosterol.

The chloroform extract of the defatted stem and leaves was fractionated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene–chloroform (8 : 2) yielded a compound NT-1 C₃₀H₅₂O₂ (*M*⁺ 444), m.p. 258–60°, [α]_D+20.94°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3360 cm⁻¹ (OH) and 1450, 1380 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl). Absence of any olefinic proton signal and presence of characteristic signals at δ 0.79–1.20 for eight methyl groups coupled with positive L.B. test suggested compound NT-I to be a saturated